

PriApp-Install: learning user privacy preferences on mobile apps' installation

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Abstract. It is undeniable that smartphones play a vital role in our lives, as their applications (called apps) can be used to access a variety of services anytime and anywhere. Despite the benefits provided by mobile apps, there are risks connected to the release of personal and sensitive data. Understanding the potential privacy risks of installing an app based on its description or privacy policy could be challenging, especially for non-skilled users. In this paper, to assist users in their app selection process, we propose PriApp-Install, a privacy-aware app installation recommendation system. It leverages semi-supervised learning to learn individual privacy preferences w.r.t mobile app installation. Learning is done based on a rich set of features modeling both the app behavior w.r.t. personal data consumption and the benefits a user can get in installing the app. We have tested four different learning strategies on a real dataset by exploiting three participant groups: security and privacy experts, IT workers, and crowd workers. The obtained results show the effectiveness of our proposal.

Keywords: Mobile apps, Privacy preferences and policies, Static analysis, Semi-supervised Learning

1 Introduction

Nowadays, smartphones are an integral part of our lives, and, as a result, we heavily rely on them and their apps. Several apps exist to support us in almost all our activities, whether these activities are related to our digital life, social life, real-life or working time. The result is that, on average, users install from 20 to 60 apps on their mobile devices.¹ This trend has relevant advantages: users benefit from different services almost everywhere. However, apps may collect sensitive information about users (e.g., users' profiles and habits) and their devices (e.g., locations), which may not be all needed for the app's execution.

To mitigate privacy risks, different privacy laws have been approved to limit service providers' requests for unnecessary information, such as GDPR² for the European countries. Also, mobile platforms have started to care more about individual privacy. As an example, Android OS introduced the **permission** and **permission group** principle, by which developers can indicate the type and scope of collected data, and apps have to request such permissions to end-users

¹ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/267309/number-of-apps-on-mobile-phones/>

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

before getting access to sensitive resources.³ These efforts reduce the set of permissions required by apps to some extent [29], but users are still largely unaware of the privacy implications of some permissions they grant to apps.

For this reason, several approaches have recently been proposed to develop recommendation systems supporting users in making more privacy-aware decisions on app’s installation. However, the majority of them (a) assign a risk score to target apps and (b) suggest not to install apps with an high risk score. Therefore, their main focus is the definition of the risk score metric. For instance, some approaches suggest determining the risk by comparing the app’s requested permissions with the app’s description [3,27]. Other studies focus on static analysis of app’s code to capture the app’s behavior w.r.t personal data collection (see Section 6 for more details).

However, we believe that these approaches do not fully support end-users in the app installation process. Focusing only on the risk of an app w.r.t personal data consumption, they ignore other relevant factors to be taken into account when installing an app. First, the possible risk must be compared with the benefits that an app can bring to a specific user. For instance, a user may decide to install a risky medical app since it collects sensitive information because it is essential for him/her as it monitors a disease he/she suffers. The other important aspect is that privacy is subjective by nature, and therefore one-size-fits-all solutions do not properly work. Users might have different opinions w.r.t. the installation of apps with the same risk level.

To cope with all these issues, this paper proposes PriApp-Install, a tool whose goal is to learn user preferences on app installation to suggest whether to install a new app or not.⁴ Learning exploits three main dimensions: the app’s behavior w.r.t. personal data usage; the benefits that installing the app could bring to target users; and the sharing of collected personal information with third parties. All this information is collected through (a) the app market, (b) the static analysis of the app’s code, and (c) the analysis of the app’s privacy policy.

To balance users’ effort and the prediction quality, we opt for semi-supervised learning [24]. In particular, we have experimentally tested four different learning strategies over the selected features, and we show that, among different semi-supervised approaches, the ones that better fit the considered scenario are those based on ensemble learning [14,16]. We also show that semi-supervised learning provides better accuracy than supervised approaches (i.e., random forest, linear regression, and SVM) even with a small training dataset.

We have tested our learning approaches with three different groups of participants. First, we considered the feedback of 51 cybersecurity and privacy experts (S&P experts) who work in academic institutions. We then collected feedback from 90 IT workers, i.e., junior and senior developers in industrial institutions from different countries. Finally, we used a crowd-sourcing platform to have a more significant (i.e., 300 participants), more balanced (i.e., gender, ages), and more heterogeneous (i.e., different nationalities and education levels) dataset.

³ <https://developer.android.com/guide/topics/permissions/overview>

⁴ <https://gitfront.io/r/user-1848964/KfsiKHgnMtLr/PriApp-Install/>

The obtained results show that around 94.51% of S&P experts, 86.39% of IT workers, and 80.69% of crowd workers were satisfied with the app installation decisions suggested by our tool.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the overall architecture of PriApp-Install. Sections 3 and 4 present the adopted learning approaches and dataset, respectively. The evaluation and related work are presented in Sections 5 and 6, respectively. Section 7 concludes the paper. Finally, the appendix includes information about the adopted metrics, app installation behavior survey, and overview of the considered APIs.

2 Overall architecture

PriApp-Install aims at assisting users in deciding whether to install an Android app or not. The decision is mainly based on the privacy risks related to the information collected and shared with third parties and the benefits the users might get from the app. Moreover, in developing our tool, we acknowledge that users might have different perceptions of privacy risks implied by apps' data collection [9], or more in general of privacy, as well as, on possible benefits. To consider this subjective dimension, PriApp-Install leverages semi-supervised learning to build a classifier for predicting decisions about apps' installation based on users' feedback.

The learning process relies on a rich set of features describing different aspects of the target app relevant to the decision process (see Appendix B for the motivation for the selection of these features). First of all, thanks to the information available in app store⁵, we obtain some *app's basic information*, including the app's name, developers' name, app's category, app's description, and so on.

Additionally, we consider the *app's privacy policy* to collect other relevant information. In particular, we parse the privacy policy to determine the declared purposes for data collection and third-party usage. We focus on these information because they are always present in the analyzed apps' privacy policies. In contrast, other information, such as the retention period (i.e., for how long the server stores the data), is present only in a few apps' privacy policies. However, this publicly available app's information is not sufficient for users to fully understand the app's behavior w.r.t personal data consumption. To overcome this limitation, PriApp-Install also considers the *app's source code* to determine which data is collected by an app.

In particular, in this paper, we leverage on the static analysis tool developed in [19] to model and capture the API usage w.r.t. the collection of personal data. [19] models the app's behavior w.r.t personal data collection through the definition of the *app's signature* which is generated through the static analysis of the app's source code. In particular, given a data type dt and an app app , [19] models its behavior w.r.t. collection of data of type dt as an array $sign_{app}^{dt}$, containing an element for each specific API able to retrieve a data of dt 's type. $sign_{app}^{dt}$'s

⁵ Android app store: <https://play.google.com/store/apps>

elements have value 1, if the corresponding API is present in *app*'s source code; 0, otherwise. [19] focuses on seven types of personal data, namely: user location (e.g., city, country), media (e.g., users' image, video, audio), connection (e.g., activity on Bluetooth, NFC), hardware (e.g., camera, USB devices), telephony (e.g., contacts info, phone number), user profile (e.g., gender, name), and health & fitness (e.g., heart rate, body fat). Therefore, the app's signature consists of seven arrays $sign_{app}^{dt}$, one for each of the considered data type *dt*.

By analyzing 30 permissions with significant security/privacy impact, provided by Google⁶, [19] has determined 66 potentially dangerous APIs that collect data of the above-mentioned data types (see Appendix C). The app signature is therefore an array of 66 elements, corresponding to: $sign_{app}^{Loc}$ (6), $sign_{app}^{Med}$ (24), $sign_{app}^{Con}$ (13), $sign_{app}^{Har}$ (8), $sign_{app}^{Tel}$ (8), $sign_{app}^{U-P}$ (2), and $sign_{app}^{H\&F}$ (5).

Example 1. Let us consider the Google Fit: Activity Tracking app ($sign_{G-F}$). For simplicity, we will focus on the Location data type only. Its corresponding array $sign_{G-F}^{Loc}$ in $sign_{G-F}$ can be defined as follow:⁷ $sign_{G-F}^{Loc} = 100000$, where the first element has value "1", representing that the android.location API is used in the app code; whereas, the other elements' value is "0" (i.e., 5 elements), since the corresponding APIs are not used in the app code.

Therefore, we model an app as a set of features extracted by its *basic information* provided in the app market, *source code* analysis, and *privacy policy*, as the following definition states. Table 1 summarizes the considered dimensions, the corresponding app's features and the way we collect them.

Table 1. *app*'s dimensions and corresponding fields

Dimension	Collection process	App's features
basic information	crawled from the app market	<i>an, dn, cat</i>
data consumption behavior	app's signature, determined via the static analysis tool proposed in [19]	<i>sign</i>
privacy policy	data collection purposes and third party usages, extracted by exploiting [26]	<i>pp, 3pt</i>

Definition 1. App's features: *Given an app, we model its features as a tuple $(an, dn, cat, sign, pp, 3pt)$, where: *an* is the app's name; *dn* is the developer's name; *cat* is the app's category; *sign* is the app's signature; whereas *pp* and *3pt* model the data collection purposes and third-party usages, respectively, as stated in the app's privacy policy. *pp* is defined as a set of pairs, each one denoting a purpose and the corresponding collected data.⁸ Finally, *3pt* is a set of triples,*

⁶ <https://developer.android.com/reference/android/Manifest.permission>

⁷ Arrays for the other personal data types can be similarly defined.

⁸ *pp* contains *not_specified* if the policy does not specify any purpose

each one denoting the third party name, the corresponding shared data and the sharing purpose.⁹

Example 2. Let us consider Google Fit: Activity Tracking app and let $sign_{G_F}$ its app signature, defined similarly to its location component $sign_{G_F}^{Loc}$ given in Example 1. According to Definition 1, its features are modelled as follow:

$GoogleFit=(Google\ Fit: Activity\ Tracking, Google\ LLC, Health\&\ Fitness, sign_{G_F}, \{(analysis, user\ profile), (marketing, not_specified), (maintenance, \{location, user\ profile\})\}, \{(ads, Google\ Ads, not_specified)\})$.

To learn user judgment w.r.t apps' installation, we build a labeled training dataset $LApp$, by asking users to assign a judgment (label) for each *app* in the training set. This judgment indicates whether the user wants to install the corresponding app or not, based on its features (see Definition 1). If the user finds the provided information insufficient, he/she may decline to respond. The corresponding labels are therefore: Yes (Y), No (N), and Maybe (M). We used $LApp$ to test different learning approaches described in the next section.

3 Learning Approaches

Literature offers several learning approaches that could be used for our goal. However, as mentioned in Section 2, we opt for semi-supervised learning [24], which has the advantage of achieving good accuracy with a small labeled training set (see subsect. 5.3). It allows us not to require users to label many apps since this would negatively impact the usability and acceptability of our solution. To select the best semi-supervised learning approach, we test four different learning strategies with different complexity (the results are reported in Section 5). These four strategies are described in the following sections.

3.1 Naive and category-based prediction models

As learning algorithm we exploit the Expectation-maximization (EM) algorithm [2]. EM is an iterative method to find maximum likelihood or maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimates of θ parameters¹⁰ in statistical models, where the model depends on unobserved latent variables. The EM algorithm alternates between an expectation (E) and a maximization (M) steps. The first step computes the maximum likelihood estimation for θ , quantified by the log-likelihood of all the items, based on the current estimation for θ parameters. In the second step, the algorithm updates θ to maximize the likelihood. In our case, the first step trains a classifier with only the available labeled apps and uses the classifier to assign probabilistically weighted class labels to each target app, by calculating the expectation of the missing class labels. The algorithm, then, trains a new classifier using all the apps (i.e., both the original labeled, pseudo-labeled apps).

⁹ If shared data are not specified in the privacy policy, *3pt* is set to *not_specified*.

¹⁰ θ parameters aim at optimizing the label probability.

Our baseline is a naive approach that considers all *app*'s features (i.e., *an*, *dn*, *cat*, *sign*, *pp*, *3pt*) to predict the pseudo-labels of the target apps.

The second approach, i.e., category-based, takes in consideration that apps belonging to the same category might have similar behavior (in terms of required personal data). At this aim, the category-based approach groups all apps with the same category to build the classifier pseudo-labeling the target apps.

Algorithm 1 EM(*LApp*,*UApp*)

```

1: input: the set of labeled apps LApp, the set of unlabeled apps UApp.
2: output: labels for UApp.
3: for each appi ∈ UApp do
4:    $\theta = \text{EM}(LApp)$ ;
5:   Calculate log-likelihood  $L(\theta)$ ;
6:   convergence = false;
7:   Dataset = LApp ∪ {appi};
8:   while convergence==false do
9:     E-step: Estimate likelihood on Dataset based on  $\theta$  parameter values;
10:    M-step: Update  $\theta$  parameter values;
11:    Calculate new log-likelihood  $L(\theta_{new})$ ;
12:    if  $|L(\theta_{new}) - L(\theta)| \leq \epsilon$  then
13:      convergence=true;
14:       $lab_{app_i} = \text{argmax}_g(p(app_i, lab_{app_i} | \theta)p(\theta))$ ;
15:      UApp = UApp - {appi};
16:      LApp = LApp ∪ {(appi, labappi)};
17:    else
18:       $L(\theta) = L(\theta_{new})$ ;
19:    end if
20:  end while
21: end for
22: return LApp;
```

Algorithm 1 describes how the pseudo-labels of each app in the unlabeled dataset are generated using the EM algorithm. This algorithm is used both for naive and category-based approaches. In the case of the naive approach, Algorithm 1 receives as *LApp* all apps. In contrast, in the case of category-based, we pass to Algorithm 1 only apps with the same category. The algorithm is thus re-executed for each category, obtaining a different prediction model.

Algorithm 1 executes EM to estimate the θ parameters using only the labeled dataset, i.e., *LApp*, and the pseudo-labeled apps from the previous iteration (see line 4). Line 5 calculates the initial value of the log-likelihood $L(\theta)$. The expectation step calculates the membership probability for each app and each label (i.e., yes, no, maybe) (line 9). In the maximization step, parameters are optimized for each label based on the current membership probability (line 10). The expectation and maximization phases are iterated until log-likelihood does not change (i.e., the difference between values of log-likelihood computed in two subsequent iterations is less than a value ϵ (see line 12)). Then, the pseudo-label returned for each app (*app_i*) is associated with the highest membership probability (line 14).¹¹ Algorithm 1 repeatedly labels the unlabeled apps in *UApp* until this set is empty (the for-loop from line 3 to line 21). Finally, it returns *LApp*, including the original labeled apps and the pseudo-labeled ones (line 22).

¹¹ **argmax** is used for finding the label (i.e., Y, N, MB) with the highest probability.

3.2 Simple and advanced ensemble-based prediction models

The first two approaches benefit from being efficient in terms of time required for building the prediction model [23]. However, they do not exploit all the features (e.g., location data collected in *sign*) as well as correlations that might exist among the considered features, which can affect the accuracy during label prediction [10]. We believe that different combinations of apps’ features might impact the prediction models, and thus the app installation decisions. For instance, prior studies have found that knowledge of the data collection purposes (i.e., *pp*), as well as third party usages (i.e., *3pt*), can increase user awareness when installing an app [8,25].

For these reasons, we further apply two ensemble-based algorithms with the aim of better capturing user behavior w.r.t app’s installation. Ensemble-based learning combines a group of sub-classifiers to create a more robust prediction model [13]. In practice, we use ensemble learning to define prediction models on the app’s feature subsets. Then, we combine the most confident one.

Table 2. Classifiers for the simple (Sim) and advanced (Adv) ensemble-based approach

	Classifier 1 features	Classifier 2 features	Classifier 3 features
Sim	<i>an, dn, cat</i>	<i>sign</i>	<i>pp, 3pt</i>
Adv	<i>an, dn, cat, sign</i>	<i>sign, pp, 3pt</i>	<i>pp, 3pt, an, dn, cat</i>

Algorithm 2 implements the simple ensemble-based approach. It exploits the app’s features corresponding to each app’s dimension to define a different classifier (line 3). Once the classifiers have been built, given a target app (app_i), the **Ensemble** algorithm identifies to which label app_i most likely belongs to by using the bagging method [14] (see lines 6 - 11). Bagging is an effective method for ensemble learning, where the final label is assigned by computing the average of membership probabilities returned by the obtained classifiers (line 12). Algorithm 2 repeatedly labels the unlabeled apps in $UApp$ until $UApp$ is empty (the for-loop from lines 4 to 15). Finally, the algorithm returns $LApp$, including the original labeled apps and the pseudo-labeled apps (line 16).

Implementation of the advanced ensemble-based approach is similar to that of the simple ensemble-based one (Algorithm 2), being the only difference the app’s features used to build the classifiers, which are those reported in Table 2.

In particular, in the first approach, called simple ensemble-based, we build three separate classifiers based on the three dimensions according to which we classify an app’s features (cfr. Table 1). As reported in the first row of Table 2, the first classifier is built only on *an*, *dn*, and *cat* features; the second on the *sign* feature; and the third on *pp* and *3pt* features.

In contrast, in the second approach, called advanced ensemble-based learning, we build three classifiers exploiting correlations among features belonging to different dimensions. Indeed, users might have different opinions on apps by

Algorithm 2 Simple_Ensemble($LApp, UApp$)

```

1: input: labeled apps  $LApp$ , unlabeled apps  $UApp$ .
2: output: labels for  $UApp$ .
3: Let  $dimension = \{(an, dn, cat), sign, (pp, 3pt)\}$ 
4: for each  $app_i \in UApp$  do
5:    $\theta_{ens} = EM(LApp)$ ;
6:   for  $X \in dimension$  do
7:     Let  $LApp_X$  be the projection of  $LApp$  on  $X$ ;
8:     Let  $app_{iX}$  be the projection of  $app_i$  on  $X$ ;
9:      $\theta_X = EM(LApp_X, app_{iX})$ ;
10:     $\theta_{ens} = \theta_{ens} \cup \theta_X$ ;
11:   end for
12:    $lab_{app_i} = \mathit{argmax}_{\theta_{ens}} (p(app_i, lab_{app_i} | \theta_{ens}) p(\theta_{ens}))$ ;
13:    $UApp = UApp - \{app_i\}$ ;
14:    $LApp = LApp \cup \{(app_i, lab_{app_i})\}$ ;
15: end for
16: return  $LApp$ ;

```

considering features of different dimensions simultaneously. As an example, Lin et al. [6] found that users are not willing to install dictionary apps since they access their locations (i.e., data collection). However, when users realize that this data is needed to compute location-based trending words (i.e., purpose), they are fine to install them. As such, we believe that features of different dimensions should be combined together. For this purpose, in the advanced ensemble-based approach, we design each classifier to combine two out of the three dimensions. For instance, the first classifier is built by considering features belonging to the first and second dimension, namely an, dn, cat , and $sign$, whereas the second classifier combines features belonging to the second and third dimension (see the second row of Table 2). Figure 1 describes the architecture of PriApp-Install and the supported learning strategies.

Fig. 1. PriApp-Install architecture

4 Dataset

To generate the app dataset to test our learning strategies, we selected a list of the most-downloaded apps from 15 popular categories. Table 3 reports the

considered categories. In total, we crawled 32,856 apps in Feb. 2021. We crawled app’s basic information from the app market, namely app’s name, developer’s name, and category. Also, we downloaded the APK files of the selected apps.

Table 3. App dataset

Category	Java code (#apps)	Privacy policy (#apps)	Category	Java code (#apps)	Privacy policy (#apps)	Category	Java code (#apps)	Privacy policy (#apps)
Beauty	1311	1061	Food & Drink	2115	1515	Shopping	2087	1537
Business	2258	1568	Health & Fitness	1546	1167	Social	1506	1158
Education	2249	1782	Maps & Navigation	1606	1240	Sports	1655	1303
Entertainment	1838	1407	Medical	1733	1232	Tools	1799	1387
Finance	2225	1747	Music & Audio	1425	1203	Travel & Local	1857	1513

To generate the app’s signature, we first leveraged decompiler reverse engineering to obtain the Java code from the corresponding APK (CFR. Figure 1). Among the 32,856 crawled apps, we successfully decompiled 27,210 of them (about 82.82%).¹² Then, we applied the static analysis approach in [19] to collect the APIs usage for the seven considered data types (i.e., 66 APIs), namely location, media, connection, hardware, telephony, user profile, and health & fitness. To determine if a declared API is exploited by an app, we checked whether the functions/constants of the target API are used in the app’s source code.

To minimize the amount of information that participants to our experiments must check, we show only the information on API usage for each target app (66 APIs), rather than information on classes (nearly 1.4K classes) or functions/constants usage (more than 13.6K functions/constants).¹³

Finally, to analyze privacy policies to determine data collection purposes and third-party usage, we exploited the natural language processing (NLP) tool defined by Wilson et al. in [26]. Among all 27,210 decompiled apps, we successfully collected privacy policies of 20,820 apps (approximately 76.52%). For data collection purposes (i.e., component *pp* of Definition 1), we considered the 18 most popular ones, such as Profiling, Analysis, Statistical, Advertisements, Maintenance. We also determined the corresponding collected data (by restricting our analysis to the seven personal data types) for each purpose mentioned in the app’s privacy policy. Additionally, we captured the third-party usage (i.e., component *3pt* of Definition 1) by extracting from the privacy policy the name of the third party with which data are shared, the corresponding usage purposes, and collected data. For usage purposes, we considered the five most common ones (i.e., Payment, Delivery, Marketing, Advertisement, and Analysis).

5 Experiments

We carried out several experiments to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed learning approaches in capturing users’ preferences regarding app’s installation.

¹² Failure to decompile was primarily due to code obfuscation.

¹³ On average, we are collected dataset with an app using about 6 APIs, 48 classes, and 238 functions/constants to collect personal data.

5.1 Experiments Setting

In our experiments, users have been involved both to label the training set and evaluate if a prediction model has correctly labeled a target app. For this purpose, we developed a web application through which participants label the training apps in the learning phase (i.e., training dataset), and give their feedback on the labels generated by the prediction models in the testing phase (i.e., test dataset). During the learning phase, participants are asked to associate a decision (i.e., Y, N, M) with ten apps that belong to two categories, randomly selected from the 15 categories in Table 3 (i.e., five apps/category). For each app, we show its features (those listed in Definition 1), namely: app’s name, developer’s name, category, its signature, data collection purposes, and third-party usages.

Once the labeling phase is terminated, the collected training dataset is elaborated by the learning algorithms illustrated in Section 3, namely the naive, category-based, simple ensemble-based, and advanced ensemble-based approach. To evaluate the learning strategies, the web application shows 16 new apps to the experiment’s participants to build the test dataset for the four proposed approaches (i.e., four target apps/approaches). For each target app, the participants give feedback on the labels, i.e., agree (Y) or disagree (N) - and in case of disagreement, they provide the correct label. Finally, the web application asks the participants whether they are satisfied with the labels assigned by the four approaches. The participant can answer with yes, no, or maybe.

In the survey, we set a timer to track how long participants spend in evaluating an app. Reading basic app information takes on average 26 seconds, whereas participants spend approx. 46 seconds to (a) check information regarding API usages (i.e., app’s signature) and privacy policy (i.e., third party usage, and data collection purposes) and (b) answer the proposed questions. The total average time to complete the survey is therefore approximately 30 minutes for 26 apps (i.e., 11 and 19 minutes for the training and test phase, respectively).

5.2 Participants

We selected three groups of participants to evaluate our prediction models’ accuracy and app installation suggestions.

The first group includes S&P experts who work in academic institutions. For the recruitment process, we send the invitation email to the members of different S&P research groups. Specifically, we collected feedback from 51 S&P experts in different countries (e.g., USA, Italy, Switzerland, Germany, Belgium, Greece, Vietnam, Morocco). Participants have an average age of 28.9 (from 24 to 42). 84.31% of them were male (43 participants). Among the 51 participants, 14 are lecturers/professors, whereas the others are Ph.D. students and post-docs.

The participants in the first group have a strong background in security and privacy. However, not all of them work on software or mobile development. Therefore, to check if this background impacts the results, IT workers were selected as the second group to assess the predictions of our models. We collected

high-quality feedback from 90 IT workers, junior and senior developers in industrial institutions from different countries (e.g., France, Singapore, Vietnam, Taiwan, and Australia). IT workers have an average age of 29.6 (between 23 and 38). Among these participants, 18.88% (17 participants) were female. For the geographical distribution, 86.67% are working in Asian countries (78 participants), whereas the remaining participants are working in European countries (10 participants - 11.11%) and Australia (2 participants - 2.22%).

The third group aims at ensuring a good number of participants from different regions, nationalities, ages, and educational levels. At this purpose, we used the Microworkers crowdsourcing platform¹⁴ for the enrollment of participants (called workers). To achieve diversity in evaluating the prediction models, we selected participants from five different regions. The regions are Latin America (e.g., Brazil, Argentina, Venezuela), USA - Western (e.g., USA, Canada, Australia), Western Europe (e.g., Italy, Spain, France), Eastern Europe (e.g., Poland, Greece, Hungary), Asia & Africa (e.g., Singapore, Vietnam, Ethiopia). For each geographic area, we try to balance gender, nationalities, ages, and educational levels. Specifically, we received 60 feedback per geographic area - a total of 300 participants - 157 - of them 52.33% were male. The participants came from 81 countries (e.g., UK, Italy, India, Spain, Portugal, USA), with an average age of 28.2, being the oldest worker 48, and the youngest 18. Also, they have different educational levels (e.g., student, bachelor) and backgrounds (e.g., accountant, teacher, manager). Moreover, nearly 60% of the participants reported to have a bachelor's degree or equivalent, whereas 10% of them had a master's degree or a Ph.D. The workers were given \$1.5 for each successful feedback.

As the proposed approach depends on the participants' input on the training and testing datasets, we removed low-quality feedback. We use three characteristics to detect low-quality feedback: time to complete the survey, the number of labelled apps, and the workers corresponding answers. Therefore, we measured how much time a user devotes to give feedback for an app. If it was less than a desirable time (1 minutes/app), we suspect that the participant did not read the app's information carefully; thus, his/her feedback was removed from the dataset. As we want to analyze the accuracy and satisfaction level for all four approaches, participants' feedback was considered only when they have evaluated all 26 apps. Finally, we removed feedback from participants that gave a unique label to all apps (e.g., Maybe for all the 26 apps). In total, we removed 45 low-quality feedback from 8 experts, 7 IT workers, and 30 crowd workers.

5.3 Evaluation

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed learning approaches, we measure the accuracy, precision, recall and F1 (see Appendix A for more details).

In the first experiment, we compare the accuracy of the proposed prediction models, namely naive, category-based, simple ensemble-based, and advanced ensemble-based. In the second experiment, we compare the accuracy obtained by

¹⁴ <https://www.microworkers.com/>

our semi-supervised approaches with the ones obtained through traditional supervised learning techniques (i.e., Linear Regression, Random Forest, and SVM).

Prediction models’ accuracy In this experiment, we test the accuracy of PriApp-Install prediction models in labelling target apps in *UApp*. As shown in Figure 2, around 72.22%, 76.72% and 78.27% of S&P experts, **crowd workers**, and IT workers’ choices in labeling app installation are correctly predicted by the naive prediction model, respectively. It is the lowest accuracy of the four prediction models. Whereas, simple ensemble-based and advanced ensemble-based have the highest accuracy for predicting the app installation decisions, with around 89.22% and 92.89% for S&P experts, 86.24% and 84.79% for crowd workers, and 86.29% and 84.21% for IT workers. For the remaining models, approximately 78.04%, 79.63%, and 80.04% of the labeling predictions done by the category-based model are made correctly for crowd workers, S&P experts, and IT workers, respectively. This experiment shows that the performance of both ensemble approaches is better than those of the other approaches. In particular, the ensemble-based approaches capture the app installation behavior of S&P experts with outstanding accuracy (about 90%). It highlights that relationships among elements of an app play a vital role in the participants’ decisions.

Fig. 2. Four prediction models’ accuracy

Fig. 3. Participants satisfaction level

Satisfaction level For this experiment, the web application showed participants a set of apps with the labels generated by our prediction models and asked them if they were satisfied with the model decisions. In the testing phase, 16 target apps and corresponding predictions were presented to participants (4 apps for each approach, randomly presented to the participants).

As shown in Figure 3, around 66.67% of S&P experts, 62.80% of crowd workers, and 77.84% of IT workers are satisfied with the decisions taken using the naive prediction model, and this represents the lowest satisfaction level of the four prediction models; whereas around 73.15%, 79.63%, and 81.13% are fine with the decisions taken using the category-based prediction model. The highest satisfaction levels are obtained with the ensemble-based prediction models. Specifically, the satisfaction level of the decisions taken by advanced ensemble-based model ranges from 80.69% (crowd workers) to 94.51% (S&P experts); whereas, the satisfaction level of the simple ensemble-based model ranges from

80.16% (crowd workers) to 93.46% (S&P experts). This experiment further confirms that ensemble approaches outperform the others.

The difference between the two ensemble-based approaches is that if the simple ensemble-based approach considers essential relationships among the app's features of the same type, the advanced ensemble-based approach considers a combination of dimensions. These relationships may affect the app installation decision of the participants. Indeed, some participants' feedback points out that combining the app's fields (which is exploited by the ensemble-based prediction models) is essential for predicting the labels of target apps. For instance, **Expert 27**: “I will install the app if it does not collect my location ... the collected data is used for healthcare purposes”; **Crowd 181** : “I don't want to use apps that collect too much personal information and share it with third parties...”; or **IT-worker 31**: “... In the same app's category, I only install the app in the same app's category if I know the collected data and its purposes ...”.

Fig. 4. Accuracy of the EM-based naive prediction models vs SVM, Random Forest, and Linear Regression

Supervised vs. semi-supervised learning As mentioned in Section 3, we select semi-supervised EM as our learning approach, because we aim at reducing participant burden on the training dataset. Nevertheless, we also tested the performance of hard clustering supervised machine learning techniques. For this purpose, we compare the accuracy of our EM-based naive prediction model against three supervised hard-clustering algorithms, namely Linear Regression, Random Forest, and SVM. We use the naive prediction model to compare since it is the weakest among the four proposed models. The naive approach exploits all app's features to define the prediction model. Figure 4 shows the results, with a training dataset consisting of 6 apps and a testing dataset of 16 apps. We randomly selected 6 training apps instead of 10 since we would like to analyze the performance given a small training dataset.

The results show that the performance of our naive prediction model is the highest for the three participant groups (see Figure 4). Moreover, the accuracy of the three supervised hard-clustering prediction models is less than that of the naive prediction model because these models need more extensive training datasets for the prediction process. This motivates us to use semi-supervised rather than supervised learning.

Table 4. Comparison of the four prediction models for the test dataset

		Naive prediction model			Category-based prediction model			Simple ensemble-based prediction model			Advanced ensemble-based prediction model		
		Y (%)	N (%)	M (%)	Y (%)	N (%)	M (%)	Y (%)	N (%)	M (%)	Y (%)	N (%)	M (%)
S&P experts (N=51)	Precision	63.38	82.61	71.05	78.79	81.54	78.82	92.31	86.49	88.46	94.53	86.36	94.87
	Recall	90.00	60.00	76.06	69.33	85.48	84.81	83.72	96.97	88.46	95.28	95.00	84.09
	F1	74.38	69.51	73.46	73.76	83.47	81.71	87.81	91.43	88.46	94.90	90.48	89.16
IT workers (N=90)	Precision	83.33	67.54	84.19	75.48	85.50	80.00	91.18	89.10	76.92	81.11	87.50	91.22
	Recall	75.43	81.91	78.17	81.25	75.68	82.76	81.58	89.10	90.10	94.81	68.86	74.29
	F1	79.19	74.94	81.07	78.26	80.29	81.36	86.11	89.10	83.33	87.45	77.06	81.89
Crowd workers (N=300)	Precision	79.12	74.59	76.43	74.61	80.70	79.04	87.35	84.02	87.23	85.06	81.73	86.00
	Recall	82.42	71.65	76.43	78.28	76.35	79.34	86.54	88.26	83.25	94.05	66.93	73.71
	F1	80.74	73.09	76.43	76.40	78.46	79.19	86.94	86.13	85.19	89.33	73.59	79.38

Table 5. Comparison of the four prediction models for the training dataset

		Naive prediction model			Category-based prediction model			Simple ensemble-based prediction model			Advanced ensemble-based prediction model		
		Y (%)	N (%)	M (%)	Y (%)	N (%)	M (%)	Y (%)	N (%)	M (%)	Y (%)	N (%)	M (%)
S&P experts (N=51)	Precision	61.19	80.30	68.67	69.12	72.73	74.39	83.33	92.11	78.57	80.00	94.40	82.93
	Recall	75.93	61.63	75.00	75.81	64.00	77.22	90.91	81.40	84.62	90.00	92.91	77.27
	F1	67.77	69.74	71.70	72.31	68.09	75.78	86.96	86.42	81.48	84.71	93.65	80.00
IT workers (N=90)	Precision	75.69	65.22	80.36	76.12	72.85	76.24	81.48	88.00	75.00	76.92	79.55	84.21
	Recall	71.12	79.79	71.43	68.92	76.39	79.31	80.00	80.49	85.71	65.57	90.91	68.57
	F1	73.33	71.77	75.63	72.34	74.58	77.75	80.73	84.08	80.00	70.80	84.85	75.59
Crowd workers (N=300)	Precision	75.40	71.43	67.67	76.64	68.70	72.50	79.92	86.94	77.78	72.07	84.44	77.91
	Recall	76.31	66.93	71.15	68.05	73.77	74.91	84.05	83.49	78.17	62.99	89.65	72.57
	F1	75.85	69.11	69.36	72.09	71.15	73.68	81.93	85.18	77.97	67.23	86.97	75.15

F1 Measure Finally, we measure the F_1 score for each label (Y, N, M) in the training and test datasets (see Tables 5 and 4, respectively). F_1 score considers both the precision and the recall aspects (see Table 7 in Appendix B). Our analysis proves that both ensemble-based approaches work better than the two remaining approaches (i.e., naive and category-based) for both the training (Table 5) and test datasets (Table 4). It means that combining multiple aspects/classifiers (i.e., ensemble-based approaches) helps predict participants' app installation decisions better for both participants with and without a security/privacy background.

From our experiments, we obtain an accuracy for the three participant groups ranging between 86.24% and 92.89%. We believe that this is acceptable since we strike a balance between the user burden and the prediction quality. However, we plan to improve our tool by testing alternative prediction models, especially for less skilled participants.

When a user decides to install Pri-App Install on his/her smartphone it takes approx 11 minutes to train the tool (with 10 sample apps) in such a way that it learns the privacy preferences of the user wrt app's installation. This training phase, although time consuming, is done only once when the tool is installed.

6 Related work

Literature offers several proposals for app recommendation. For instance, some papers propose tools to determine if target apps are benign based on over-privileged apps' detection. As an example, Taylor et al. [21,22] propose a contextual permission analysis tool, called SecuRank, which allow users to detect if any of their installed apps could be replaced with functionally similar apps that collect less sensitive data. By running SecuRank on the app market, they found that up to 50% of privacy-breaching apps could be replaced with more privacy-preserving apps. Yinglan et al. [3] develops the AC-Net framework, assessing the consistency between app's descriptions and required permissions. In particular, AC-Net analyze the description-to-permission of 1415 popular apps, leveraging on neural networks. AC-Net predicts the necessary permissions from the app's description and compared its prediction with the actual permissions of the app to detect over-privileged apps.

Exploiting the same approach, Tingmin et al. [27] introduces the PERSCRIPTION platform that aims to replace the app's description with a new personalized one based on users' preferences on security concerns and linguistic preferences. More precisely, to model user's security concerns, given a target app, PERSCRIPTION asks user to label as grant/deny all app's default permissions. Additionally, to generate the personalised description w.r.t. linguistic preferences, PERSCRIPTION classifies users into distinct personalities based on their behaviors. Specifically, they considered five personality traits models [4], (e.g., Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, and Openness) to bridge between the users' mobile behaviours (i.e., app adoption) and linguistic preferences. To each personality a set of preferred words (linguistic preference) is associated. The final app's description is then generated by using proper words, based on users personality and highlighting risky permissions.

Zhiqiang et al. [28] proposes the FideDroid framework that predicts permissions needed by an app by analyzing its description. After that, FideDroid compares the inferred permissions with those marked as suspicious and unnecessary by determining whether the predicted permissions from the app's description are used in the app's code. Moreover, Huseyin et al. [1] proposes a model, called Attention, to discover inconsistencies between the app's descriptions and the requested permissions, by leveraging on recurrent neural networks (RNNs) [5].

However, all the above-mentioned approaches: (a) only estimate the risk of installing an app without considering the possible benefits; and (b) only consider the app's requested permissions that do not accurately describe the actual behavior of an app w.r.t. the consumption of personal data. Indeed, many studies (e.g., [11]) have shown that apps could actually exploit more permissions than what they provide in the app market.

Other approaches take this issue into account by leveraging on app's code analysis. For instance, Zhang et al. [30] develops a cloud-based system, called Privet, that logs app's behavior w.r.t resources' usage (e.g., CPU, memory) and personal data collection (e.g., location, media). For dangerous API usages, Zhuo et al. [17] and Abhishek et al. [7] exploit static analysis to generate a graph

representation of the data flow among API classes and possibly personal data collection. These graphs are trained on a set of malicious and benign apps. The two graphs are then compared to determine the set of dangerous APIs. Son et al. [19,20] leverages on app’s static analysis to model an app’s behavior w.r.t data collection, on the basis of APIs, classes, functions, and constants usage. They measure an app’s risk level by quantifying how much the app’s behaviour diverges from the behavior of the majority of the apps in the same category.

Although those approaches show some similarities with our proposal, in that we also leverage on static analysis to have a more precise assessment of the app’s collected personal data (that we borrow from [19]), all these approaches only estimate the privacy risk connected to a target app. In contrast, the goal of our proposal is not to propose yet another privacy risk measure for mobile apps. Rather, we design a tool that learns from end users their preferences w.r.t app’s installation. This tool can complement the risk analysis performed by the above mentioned approaches. Learning takes into account not only the privacy risk of an app (in terms of personal data it consumes and share with third parties), but also the benefits an app can provide (in terms of delivered service), as well as the subjective aptitude that each user might have towards privacy.

7 Conclusion

This paper proposed PriApp-Install, a tool to guide users in selecting the apps to install on their smartphones, based on their subjective assessment of utility and privacy risks. PriApp-Install leverages semi-supervised learning and a rich set of features to determine user privacy preferences on app’s installation. We have experimentally tested our learning approaches by using feedback from a different set of participants (i.e., security and privacy experts, IT workers, and crowd workers). The experimental results for ensemble-based approaches are promising. In the future, we plan to perform a more extensive experimental evaluation. We also plan to test more sophisticated learning strategies, such as those combining semi-supervised classification with deep learning [15]. This combination may increase performance by, at the same time, not requiring a considerable amount of resources, time, and effort [12]. We also plan to extend our approach to detect mismatches between an app’s privacy policy and its actual behavior w.r.t personal data usage. Finally, we plan to extend the current approach to be adopted in the Personal Data Storage (PDS) [18] architecture, where users can store and control access to their personal data.

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Appendix A: Metrics

We use conventional measures to measure the effectiveness of the proposed learning approaches. In particular, since we have classes with three labels (Y, N, and M), we exploit a 3×3 confusion matrix, see Table 6, where columns represent predicted labels, rows possible actual value and cells denote error value (E) or true positive value (TP). From the confusion matrix, we define the evaluation metrics given in Table 7.

Table 6. Confusion matrix

	Predicted value: Y	Predicted value: N	Predicted value: M
Actual value: Y	TP_Y	$E_{Y,N}$	$E_{Y,M}$
Actual value: N	$E_{N,Y}$	TP_N	$E_{N,M}$
Actual value: M	$E_{M,Y}$	$E_{M,N}$	TP_M

Table 7. Metrics definition

$$\begin{array}{l|l}
 Accuracy & (TP_Y + TP_N + TP_M) / \#samples \\
 Pre_X & TP_X / (TP_X + E_{N,X} + E_{M,X}) \\
 Re_X & TP_X / (TP_X + E_{X,N} + E_{X,M}) \\
 2*F1_X & 2 * (Pre_X * Re_X) / (Pre_X + Re_X) \\
 & \text{where } X \in \{Y, N, M\}
 \end{array}$$

Appendix B: App installation behavior survey

The proposed approach relies on a set of features describing different aspects of the target app (i.e., *an*, *cat*, *dn*, *sign*, *pp*, and *3pt*). We have selected these

features under the assumption that they are relevant to deciding to install or not an app. To validate this assumption, we run a survey asking participants of our experiments to judge the relevance of each feature in making the decision. In particular, for each feature, they have to select the importance level (by selecting a value from a five-point Likert scale: Very unimportant - Very important). Additionally, in the survey, we added four new features for the app's basic info: app's description, number of downloads, picture & video, ratings & reviews.

Table 8. Survey of features relevance in deciding app installation.

		App's basic infor							App's code			App's privacy policy	
		App's name (an)	Category (cat)	Developer's name (dn)	Description	Number of downloads	Picture & video	Ratings & reviews	Collected data (sign)	Purposes (pp)	Third party (3pt)		
S&P experts (N = 51)	Very unimportant	9(18%)	5(10%)	5(10%)	5(10%)	13(25%)	23(45%)	21(41%)	2(4%)	0(0%)	3(6%)		
	Unimportant	2(4%)	2(4%)	12(24%)	12(24%)	12(24%)	20(39%)	16(31%)	2(4%)	0(0%)	3(6%)		
	Neutral	5(10%)	15(29%)	7(14%)	14(27%)	8(16%)	5(10%)	11(22%)	10(20%)	12(24%)	15(29%)		
	Important	13(25%)	17(33%)	10(20%)	12(24%)	10(20%)	1(2%)	2(4%)	15(29%)	12(24%)	12(24%)		
IT workers (N = 90)	Very important	22(43%)	12(24%)	17(33%)	8(16%)	8(16%)	2(4%)	1(2%)	22(43%)	27(52%)	18(35%)		
	Very unimportant	12(13%)	13(14%)	8(9%)	18(20%)	32(36%)	42(47%)	37(41%)	8(9%)	9(10%)	10(11%)		
	Unimportant	5(6%)	4(4%)	9(10%)	22(24%)	21(23%)	22(24%)	29(32%)	2(2%)	2(2%)	13(14%)		
	Neutral	14(16%)	12(13%)	15(17%)	20(22%)	11(12%)	16(18%)	15(17%)	15(17%)	7(8%)	15(17%)		
Crowd workers (N = 300)	Important	28(31%)	34(38%)	24(27%)	16(18%)	12(13%)	3(3%)	4(4%)	30(33%)	19(21%)	20(22%)		
	Very important	31(34%)	27(30%)	34(38%)	14(16%)	14(16%)	7(8%)	5(6%)	35(39%)	53(59%)	32(36%)		
	Very unimportant	45(15%)	42(14%)	27(9%)	60(20%)	45(15%)	48(16%)	47(16%)	24(8%)	24(8%)	30(10%)		
	Unimportant	15(5%)	12(4%)	36(12%)	50(17%)	72(24%)	76(25%)	58(19%)	6(2%)	6(2%)	36(12%)		
Crowd workers (N = 300)	Neutral	42(14%)	45(15%)	60(20%)	45(15%)	61(20%)	53(18%)	73(24%)	51(17%)	30(10%)	57(19%)		
	Important	93(31%)	111(37%)	78(26%)	67(22%)	58(19%)	62(21%)	69(23%)	99(33%)	66(22%)	69(23%)		
	Very important	105(35%)	90(30%)	99(33%)	78(26%)	64(21%)	61(20%)	53(18%)	120(40%)	174(58%)	108(36%)		

The results of the survey is presented in Table 8. Here, we can see that more than 60% of S&P experts consider the collected data *sign* (37-73%), purpose *pp* (39-76%), and third party *3pt* (33-65%) important/very important to take the decision on app installation. Whereas, the percentage of IT workers considering these features important/very important are: 72% for *sign*, 80% for *pp*, 58% for *3pt*. Besides, 77% (219) of crowd workers believe that the collected data is necessary for the app installation; 80% (240) and 59% (177) of crowd workers also believe the purposes and third party are important, respectively. Regarding app' basic features, we can see two main groups of important and neutral & unimportant features. The former includes the app's name (*an*), category (*cat*), and developer's name (*dn*) with the percentage of (very) important label higher than 50%. The latter includes the remaining features (i.e., app's description, number of downloads, picture&video, and ratings&reviews), with percentage of (very) important label less than 50%.

Appendix C: Selected APIs

The selected APIs' list and their URL are shown in Table 10. The amount of functions/constants of these 66 selected APIs is around 17k. To have a more efficient analysis, we focused only on functions/constants related to the seven personal data types. The number of classes, functions/constants is shown in Table 9 for each data type.

Table 9. Examples of collected data for each data type, the number of analyzed APIs, classes, and functions/constants

Data type	Collected data	APIs	Classes	Functions/Constants
Location	Longitude, latitude, address, public places	6	92	1189
Media	Image, media metadata, audio, video	24	588	5362
Connection	IP address, wifi, bluetooth, http, nfc	13	329	3215
Hardware	Device name, camera, mobile sensors	8	84	1146
Telephony	Send/receive SMS, contact, phone number	8	127	1637
User profile	Birthday, gender, name, organization	2	58	354
Health&fitness	Fitness activities, height, weight, body fat	5	82	632

Table 10. 66 selected APIs

Position	APIs	URL	Data type
1	android.location	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/location/package-summary	Location
2	com.google.android.gms.location	https://developers.google.com/android/reference/com/google/android/gms/location/package-summary	Location
3	com.google.android.gms.maps	https://developers.google.com/android/reference/com/google/android/gms/maps/package-summary	Location
4	com.google.android.gms.maps.model	https://developers.google.com/android/reference/com/google/android/gms/maps/model/package-summary	Location
5	com.google.android.gms.location.places	https://developers.google.com/android/reference/com/google/android/gms/location/places/package-summary	Location
6	com.google.android.gms.location.places.ui	https://developers.google.com/android/reference/com/google/android/gms/location/places/ui/package-summary	Location
7	android.media	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/media/package-summary	Media
8	android.media.audiofx	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/media/audiofx/package-summary	Media
9	android.media.browse	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/media/browse/package-summary	Media
10	android.media.effect	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/media/effect/package-summary	Media
11	android.media.midi	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/media/midi/package-summary	Media
12	android.media.projection	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/media/projection/package-summary	Media
13	android.media.session	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/media/session/package-summary	Media
14	android.media.tv	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/media/tv/package-summary	Media
15	android.service.media	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/service/media/package-summary	Media
16	android.support.media	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/support/media/package-summary	Media
17	android.support.media.tv	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/support/media/tv/package-summary	Media
18	android.support.v4.media	https://developer.android.com/reference/kotlin/android/support/v4/media/package-summary	Media
19	android.support.v4.media.app	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/support/v4-media-app/package-summary	Media
20	android.support.v4.media.session	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/support/v4-media-session/package-summary	Media
21	android.support.v7.media	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/support/v7/media/package-summary	Media
22	androidx.exifinterface.media	https://developer.android.com/reference/androidx/exifinterface/media/package-summary	Media
23	androidx.media	https://developer.android.com/reference/androidx/media/package-summary	Media
24	androidx.media.session	https://developer.android.com/reference/androidx/media/session/package-summary	Media
25	androidx.media.app	https://developer.android.com/reference/androidx/media/app/package-summary	Media
26	androidx.media.utils	https://developer.android.com/reference/androidx/media/utils/package-summary	Media
27	androidx.media2.common	https://developer.android.com/reference/androidx/media2/common/package-summary	Media
28	androidx.media2.player	https://developer.android.com/reference/androidx/media2/player/package-summary	Media
29	androidx.mediarouter.app	https://developer.android.com/reference/androidx/mediarouter/app/package-summary	Media
30	androidx.mediarouter.media	https://developer.android.com/reference/androidx/mediarouter/media/package-summary	Media
31	android.bluetooth	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/bluetooth/package-summary	Connection
32	android.net	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/net/package-summary	Connection
33	android.net.wifi	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/net/wifi/package-summary	Connection
34	java.net	https://developer.android.com/reference/java/net/package-summary	Connection
35	java.net.ssl	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/net/ssl/package-summary	Connection
36	android.net.http	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/net/http/package-summary	Connection
37	android.net.nsd	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/net/nsd/package-summary	Connection
38	android.net.rtp	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/net/rtp/package-summary	Connection
39	android.net.sip	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/net/sip/package-summary	Connection
40	android.net.ssl	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/net/ssl/package-summary	Connection
41	android.nfc	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/nfc/package-summary	Connection
42	android.bluetooth.le	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/bluetooth/le/package-summary	Connection
43	javax.net	https://developer.android.com/reference/javax/net/package-summary	Connection
44	android.hardware	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/hardware/package-summary	Hardware
45	android.hardware.biometrics	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/hardware/biometrics/package-summary	Hardware
46	android.hardware.camera2	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/hardware/camera2/package-summary	Hardware
47	android.hardware.camera2.params	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/hardware/camera2/params/package-summary	Hardware
48	android.hardware.display	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/hardware/display/package-summary	Hardware
49	android.hardware.fingerprint	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/hardware/fingerprint/package-summary	Hardware
50	android.hardware.input	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/hardware/input/package-summary	Hardware
51	android.hardware.usb	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/hardware/usb/package-summary	Hardware
52	android.provider	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/provider/package-summary	Telephony
53	android.telephony	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/telephony/package-summary	Telephony
54	android.telephony.cdma	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/telephony/cdma/package-summary	Telephony
55	android.telephony.data	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/telephony/data/package-summary	Telephony
56	android.telephony.emergency	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/telephony/emergency/package-summary	Telephony
57	android.telephony.ims	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/telephony/ims/package-summary	Telephony
58	android.telephony.gsm	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/telephony/gsm/package-summary	Telephony
59	android.telephony.mms	https://developer.android.com/reference/android/telephony/mms/package-summary	Telephony
60	com.google.api.services.people.v1	https://developers.google.com/resources/api-libraries/documentation/people/v1/java/latest/com/google/api/services/people/v1/package-summary.html	User profile
61	com.google.api.services.people.v1.model	https://developers.google.com/resources/api-libraries/documentation/people/v1/java/latest/com/google/api/services/people/v1/model/package-summary.html	User profile
62	com.google.android.gms.fitness	https://developers.google.com/android/reference/com/google/android/gms/fitness/package-summary	Health & Fitness
63	com.google.android.gms.fitness.data	https://developers.google.com/android/reference/com/google/android/gms/fitness/data/package-summary	Health & Fitness
64	com.google.android.gms.fitness.request	https://developers.google.com/android/reference/com/google/android/gms/fitness/request/package-summary	Health & Fitness
65	com.google.android.gms.fitness.result	https://developers.google.com/android/reference/com/google/android/gms/fitness/result/package-summary	Health & Fitness
66	com.google.android.gms.fitness.service	https://developers.google.com/android/reference/com/google/android/gms/fitness/service/package-summary	Health & Fitness